

Supplementary Documents

Title: Enhancing Lung Cancer Treatment Outcome Prediction through Semantic Feature Engineering Using Large Language Models

Supplementary Fig. S1. AUC-PRC comparison across representation strategies for 1-year survival prediction. Bars represent mean Area Under the Precision–Recall Curve (AUC-PRC) across cross-validation runs for numerical feature encoding (ENF), contextual text embedding (CTE), end-to-end transformer modeling (E2E), and the proposed Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator (GKC). Error bars denote standard deviation. Results show trends consistent with AUROC comparisons, indicating robustness under outcome imbalance.

Supplementary Fig. S2. AUC-PRC comparison of predictive classifiers trained on GKC-derived features. Mean AUC-PRC values across cross-validation runs are shown for multiple machine learning classifiers trained on semantic representations generated by the GKC framework. Error bars indicate standard deviation. Relative performance trends are consistent with AUROC-based comparisons reported in the main manuscript.

Supplementary Fig. S3. AUC-PRC results from modality ablation analysis within the GKC framework. Mean AUC-PRC values across cross-validation runs are reported for all combinations of laboratory, genomic, and medication modalities. Performance patterns mirror those observed for AUROC, supporting the robustness of multimodal integration under class imbalance.

Supplementary Table S1. Performance comparison of representation strategies for 1-year survival prediction

Model	Representation	AUC-ROC (Mean \pm 95% CI)
ENF	Numerical	0.713 (0.709–0.718)
CTE	Contextual Embedding	0.771 (0.768-0.775)
E2E	ModernBERT	0.781 (0.771-0.789)
GKC (proposed)	Semantic Summarization	0.859 (0.855-0.862)

Supplementary Note 1. Summarizer Prompt Template

1.1 Design Rationale

The Goal-oriented Knowledge Curator (GKC) framework relies on explicit, modality-aware semantic summarization to transform heterogeneous clinical inputs into compact, prognostically informative representations. Rather than treating the large language model (LLM) as a generic text encoder, we design prompts that explicitly constrain the model to perform clinically grounded synthesis aligned with survival prediction.

Across all modalities, prompt design follows three guiding principles:

1. Clinical role specification to align the model's reasoning with expert interpretation used in oncology practice.
2. Task-aligned instruction emphasizing prognostic relevance, synergistic effects, and disease severity rather than descriptive restatement.
3. Structured output enforcement to ensure consistency, interpretability, and reproducibility across patients and folds.

All prompts are executed in a strictly deterministic setting and operate exclusively on the provided patient-specific modality profiles, without retrieval augmentation or external knowledge access.

1.2 Common Prompt Structure (Shared Across Modalities)

All modality-specific prompts share a common structural backbone consisting of the following components:

- Persona definition: Assigns the LLM a modality-appropriate clinical expert role (e.g., molecular oncologist, clinical pharmacologist).
- Explicit task objectives: Clearly states that the goal is prognostic assessment related to short-term or long-term survival.
- Step-by-step reasoning guidance: Encourages holistic synthesis and interaction-aware interpretation across features.
- Strict output constraints: Enforces generation of a single JSON object conforming to a predefined schema.
- Deterministic execution constraints: Prompts are executed with temperature = 0.0 and top-k = 1 to minimize stochastic variation.

This shared structure ensures that differences in generated summaries arise from modality-specific information rather than prompt inconsistency.

1.3 Genomic Summarization Prompt

Clinical role: Molecular biologist and clinical oncologist participating in a tumor board.

Objective:

To synthesize a patient's somatic mutation profile into a prognostic interpretation by analyzing the synergistic interplay of oncogenic drivers and tumor suppressor alterations, with emphasis on tumor aggressiveness, progression risk, and therapeutic implications.

Key design features:

- Explicit instruction to reason about combinatorial mutation effects.
- Separation of favorable and unfavorable genomic indicators.

Prompt Template:

```
"""
```

```
# Persona
```

```
You are a leading molecular biologist and clinical oncologist on a tumor board.
```

```
# Task
```

```
Your primary goal is to analyze the patient's genomic profile to identify key molecular factors that that may predict short-term and long-term survival in this lung cancer patient.
```

```
- Your task is to analyze the following patient's genomic profile and provide a prognostic summary paragraph.
```

- For each mutated gene, I have provided its functional summary and associated biological pathways.
- Your summary should focus on the **synergistic effect or interplay** of the identified mutations.
- Based on the combination of these mutations, assess the patient's potential tumor behavior, aggressiveness, and possible therapeutic vulnerabilities or resistances.

Follow these steps precisely:

1. **Holistic Analysis:** Analyze the **synergistic effect and interplay** of all the provided mutations together.
2. **Identify Key Pathways:** Determine the main oncogenic pathways being activated and the tumor suppressor pathways being inactivated.
3. **Assess Implications:** Based on the combination, assess the overall tumor aggressiveness and key therapeutic implications (vulnerabilities or resistances).
4. **Synthesize and Structure:** Generate your final analysis in the specified JSON format. The "prognostic_summary" should be a detailed, 4-5 sentence narrative. The other fields should be concise lists of the most critical factors.

Crucial Instructions for Output Generation:

- Your analysis **MUST** be based strictly on the patient data provided below.
- Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and nothing else.

```
{GENE_PROFILE_BLOCK}
```

Output Format (JSON Schema)

Provide your analysis in the following JSON format:

```
{
  "prognostic_summary": "A detailed, 4-5 sentence paragraph that synthesizes all genomic findings to assess the overall prognosis, focusing on tumor aggressiveness, potential progression, and impact on short-term survival.",
  "key_prognostic_domains": {
    "oncogenic_driver_pathways_activated": ["List of key signaling pathways activated by the mutations."],
    "tumor_suppressor_pathways_inactivated": ["List of key pathways inactivated."],
    "therapeutic_implications": ["List of potential sensitivities or resistances to therapies."]
  },
  "key_positive_factors": ["A list of favorable genomic indicators, if any."],
  "key_negative_factors": ["A list of unfavorable indicators."]
}
```

1.4 Medication Modality Prompt

Clinical role: Senior clinical pharmacologist and medical oncologist.

Objective:

To infer disease burden, treatment intent, and prognosis by analyzing the interplay between anti-cancer therapies and supportive care medications, with particular focus on short-term (1-year) survival.

Key design features:

- Emphasizes interpretation of supportive care intensity as a proxy for disease severity and symptom burden.
- Encourages narrative synthesis explaining why a medication pattern implies favorable or unfavorable prognosis.

Prompt Template:

```
"""
```

```
# Persona
```

You are a senior clinical pharmacologist and medical oncologist on a Molecular Tumor Board. Your expertise lies in interpreting a patient's complete medication profile to understand their treatment journey, disease burden, and overall prognosis.

```
# Primary Goal
```

Your goal is to analyze the patient's prescribed drug classes to identify the **dominant therapeutic themes** that will most strongly influence **short-term (1-year) survival** in this lung cancer patient.

Your Step-by-Step Reasoning Task

Before generating the final JSON, you must follow this precise thought process:

1. **Identify Treatment Strategy:** Review the list of all prescribed drug classes. First, categorize them into a primary **anti-cancer strategy** (e.g., Targeted Therapy, Chemotherapy, Immunotherapy, or a combination) and **supportive care** drugs.
2. **Analyze Interplay and Context:** This is the most critical step. Analyze the **interplay** between the anti-cancer drugs and the supportive care regimen.
 - What does the intensity of the supportive care (e.g., use of Strong Opioids, G-CSF, Bone-Modifying Agents) imply about the aggressiveness of the cancer or the side effects of the primary treatment?
 - Does the specific combination of anti-cancer therapies (e.g., Chemo + Immunotherapy) indicate a standard first-line approach for aggressive disease?
3. **Synthesize a Holistic Narrative:** Weave these insights into a cohesive prognostic summary. Explain **why** this specific combination of medications leads to a favorable or unfavorable prognosis by reflecting on the patient's inferred clinical state.

Crucial Instructions for Output Generation:

- Your analysis **MUST** be based strictly on the provided drug class profiles.
- Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and nothing else.

Data: Patient's Prescribed Drug Classes

```
{DRUG_PROFILE}
```

Output Format (JSON Schema)

Provide your analysis in the following JSON format:

```
{  
  "prognostic_summary": "A detailed, 4-5 sentence paragraph that synthesizes the interplay between the anti-cancer and supportive care regimens to assess the overall prognosis.",  
  "key_treatment_themes": {  
    "primary_anti_cancer_strategy": ["List the main anti-cancer approach(es), e.g., 'Chemo-immunotherapy combination', 'Targeted Therapy (EGFR)'],  
    "inferred_disease_burden_and_status": ["Describe the patient's likely condition based on the drug profile, e.g., 'High symptom burden requiring significant supportive care', 'Tolerating aggressive first-line therapy', 'Palliative care focus']  
  },  
  "key_positive_factors": ["A list of favorable indicators, if any (e.g., 'Receiving a highly effective targeted therapy')."],  
  "key_negative_factors": ["A list of the most critical unfavorable indicators (e.g., 'Concurrent use of strong opioids and bone-modifying agents suggests painful bone metastases.')."]  
}
```

1.5 Lab Modality Prompt

Clinical role: Expert oncologist interpreting longitudinal laboratory data.

Objective:

To assess prognosis based on temporal trends and synergistic relationships among inflammatory, nutritional, and hematologic laboratory markers.

Key design features:

- Explicit instruction to analyze trajectories rather than single values.
- Emphasis on interaction between inflammation and nutrition (e.g., chronic disease anemia).
- Structured domain-level assessment of physiologic stability.

Prompt Template:

```
""
```

```
# Persona
```

You are an expert oncologist on a tumor board. Your role is to provide a prognostic assessment based on a patient's serial lab data.

Task

Your primary goal is to analyze the patient's lab profile to identify key factors that could predict **short-term (1-2 year) and long-term survival** in this lung cancer patient.

Follow these steps precisely:

- Analyze Individual Trends:** For each lab test, analyze the trajectory and stability of the 5 recent measurements in the context of its normal range.
- Assess Synergistic Effects:** Pay critical attention to the **combination of different lab values**. Analyze how their interplay reveals a broader clinical picture. For example:
 - Analyze the relationship between **inflammatory markers (e.g., Platelets, Neutrophils)** and **nutritional markers (e.g., Albumin, Hemoglobin)** to assess for conditions like systemic inflammation or anemia of chronic disease.
- Synthesize Findings into JSON:** Based on your comprehensive analysis of both individual trends and synergistic effects, construct the final JSON object as specified below.

Crucial Instructions for Output Generation:

- Your analysis **MUST** be based strictly on the patient data provided below.
- Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and nothing else.

Data

```
{LAB_DATA_BLOCK}
```

Output Format (JSON Schema)

Provide your analysis in the following JSON format and nothing else:

```
{  
  "prognostic_summary": "A detailed, 4-5 sentence paragraph that synthesizes all lab findings to assess the overall prognosis, focusing on inflammation, nutritional status, hematologic stability, and their trends.",  
  "key_prognostic_domains": {  
    "inflammation_status": "Provide status (e.g., High, Normal, Low)",  
    "nutritional_status": "Provide status (e.g., Poor, Adequate, Good)",  
    "hematologic_stability": "Provide status (e.g., Unstable, Stable)"  
  },  
  "key_positive_factors": ["A list of favorable indicators, if any."],  
  "key_negative_factors": ["A concise list of the most critical unfavorable indicators, including combinatorial factors."]  
}
```

Supplementary Note 2. Deployment Efficiency and Operational Cost Analysis

To support the practical feasibility of the proposed framework, we conducted an analysis of its computational cost and latency under the current implementation.

2.1 Computational Cost

We estimated the cost based on the average token usage per patient (approximately 3,144 input tokens and 1,622 output tokens) and the pricing of the Gemini 2.0 Flash backbone and the text-embedding-005 (Gecko) model. Under these settings, the cost to generate a complete multimodal semantic summary for a single patient is approximately \$0.00099. This low per-patient cost indicates that the framework is computationally feasible for large-scale retrospective analyses and offline clinical data processing.

2.2 Latency

We measured the end-to-end processing time required to generate summaries for a single patient, including all three modalities. The average latency was approximately 1.6 seconds per patient, demonstrating that the summarization pipeline is efficient and suitable for offline preprocessing and batch-based clinical decision support workflows.

Supplementary Note 3. Robustness Analysis under Backbone LLM Substitution

This supplementary analysis directly addresses concerns regarding reliance on a single backbone LLM by isolating the effect of backbone substitution while holding all other components of the GKC framework constant.

3.1 Objective

This analysis evaluates whether the effectiveness of the proposed GKC framework depends on the choice of backbone LLM. Specifically, we assess whether replacing the general-purpose LLM with a large biomedical-specific LLM yields qualitatively similar performance trends under an identical goal-oriented summarization and evaluation pipeline.

3.2 Model Specification

- Model: MedFound-176B
- Parameters: 176 Billion
- Training Data: A massive corpus of biomedical and clinical text.

The model was used in a zero-shot manner without task-specific fine-tuning or retrieval augmentation, consistent with the main experimental setting.

3.3 Experimental Pipeline

- Step 1: Summarization
The exact same goal-oriented prompts used in the primary GKC framework were provided to the MedFound-176B model. This generated a new set of modality-specific summaries (laboratory, genomic, and medication) for each patient in the cohort.
- Step 2: Embedding
The generated summaries for each modality were embedded using the MedFound-176B model by extracting feature representations from the final hidden layer, resulting in high-dimensional vectors (14,336 dimensions) for each summary. This dimensionality reflects the internal representation size of the backbone model and was kept unchanged to preserve consistency with the substitution analysis.
- Step 3: Downstream Classification
The three modality-specific embeddings for each patient were concatenated and used as input to the same XGBoost classifier employed throughout the main experiments. Model training and evaluation were conducted using the identical 10-times repeated 5-fold cross-validation protocol to ensure a fair comparison. All components other than the backbone LLM were held constant to isolate the effect of backbone substitution.

3.4 Result

The biomedical-specific GKC instantiation using MedFound-176B achieved a mean AUC-ROC of 0.752 (± 0.014) and a mean AUC-PRC of 0.832 (± 0.017) across cross-validation runs. These values exceed those of traditional baseline models while remaining below the optimal GKC configuration, consistent with the trends reported in the main manuscript.